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Competencies Required by Business Education Graduates for Self-Employment in South-South, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined competencies required by business education graduates for self-employment in south-south, Nigeria. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 60 Business Education post-graduate students. The entire population was used because of the manageable size of the population. A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings in the study revealed that the core competencies that are required by Business Education graduates for self-employment are; Business management ability, Personal entrepreneurial ability and Technical ability. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: The managers of Business Education programme should lay much emphasis on the acquisition of the appropriate competencies needed for self-employment of graduates of the programme, there should be a constant collaboration with the industries so as to know the appropriate skills needed for Business Education graduates to be self-employable and the Curriculum of Business Education programme should be in tandem with today's competencies that are required.

Keywords: Business Education, self employment, post graduate students

INTRODUCTION

The role of Business Education is interwoven with employment creation. Many scholars have identified Business Education as a veritable aspect of Education that can bring about employment generation and socio-economic changes in the world. According to Okoro (2013), Business Education programme can prepare students with business competencies that will enable them to create and develop new enterprises. The emphasis here is that the programme has a way of shifting the focus of students from paid employment to self-employment, with sound knowledge of the programme. A graduate of Business Education programme can compete maximally in the world of work even without the paid employment based on what the country is facing. Evidently, Business Education equips individuals for gainful employment in the public sector, to be self-employed and to be teachers of business subjects. Business Education encourages innovation. Innovation is the introduction of new things, ideas or ways of doing something (Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary, 2010). In similar vein, Nnadozie (2012) noted that innovation is the introduction of new ideas or methods and Amaewhule (2014) views innovation as innovativeness, the ability to discover new things seeking new opportunities. Business Education creates

ample opportunity for innovations. According to Lawal (2014), Business Education is the pillar to any developmental undertaking in every society. It is a vital element in the broad development of the nations and creates an enabling environment for its graduates such that they possess the ability to handle and solve the problems or difficulties within their environment. In order to function, live well, earn a living and contribute to the societal growth. Business Education constantly builds knowledge, skills, values and attitudes learnt. Business Education makes people to think, speak and behave in different dimensions which can support the growth, efficiency and effectiveness in an organization. International Labour Organisation (2020) noted that employment can be boosted by: implementing effective, properly targeted active labour market policies; enhancing the competence and increasing resources available to public employment services so that jobseekers receive adequate support and, where they are working with private employment agencies, ensuring that quality services are provided and rights respected; and implementing vocational and entrepreneurial skills programmes for paid and self-employment; investing in workers' skills development, skills upgrading and re-skilling to improve employability, in particular for those having lost or at risk of losing their job and vulnerable groups; limiting or avoiding job losses and supporting enterprises in retaining their workforce through well- designed schemes implemented through social dialogue and collective bargaining. When graduates of Business Education are equipped with requisite competencies for self-employment, they can better fulfill their roles and responsibilities in the world of work and business. Business Education programme involves courses in accounting, management, marketing and office technology and management (Esene, 2017). Students are expected to relevant competencies in their areas of specialization after graduation. Business Education graduates are expected to have wide knowledge of how to handle business operation. Business Education is conducted on two distinct levels; education for administrative support personnel in business and industry received in Universities and Colleges of Education for business teacher preparation (Cross, 2008). The National Open University of Nigeria (2008) defined Business Education as an aspect of vocational education that equips people with necessary skills and theoretical knowledge needed for performance in business world either for job occupation or self-employment. Okoro (2009) stated that Business Education means education for and about business, or training in business skills and competencies required for use in offices, clerical occupations and business policy analysis, it is a training that gives an occupational identity. Ajoma (2010) viewed Business Education as that education which provides its graduates with training in business skills and economic competencies necessary for an individual to advance in business career or to establish a business enterprise. These among others make Business Education an effective tool for entrepreneurship education, unemployment and poverty reduction as well as for natural development. Therefore, Business Education is very important since it prepares individuals for the world of work.

Aliyu (2013) stated that the purpose of Business Education stresses the need for specialized instruction to prepare students for career in business; fundamental instruction to enable students assume their economic roles as consumers, workers and citizens and background instruction to assist students in preparing them for professional careers and advance study. Ogwunte and Ile (2017) defined Business Education as that aspect of the total educational programme that provides the knowledge, skills, understanding and attitude needed to perform in the business world as a producer or consumer of goods and services that business offers. Also, the high graduate unemployment rate in Nigeria indicates an urgent need for positive work option, which is possible through Business Education training. Business Management competency and Self-Employment requires that graduates should have these skills; finance management, control, accounting, management, human relations, decision making, negotiation, planning and goal setting, venture launching, growth management (Epelle, Orlu & Okparanta, 2017). Business management competencies include the ability to supervise business effectively, ability to source funds for running of small-scale business knowledge of business registration, ability to plan for small-scale or medium-scale business, ability to be resourceful and creative, ability to develop skills for the graduate growth and development of firm, ability to develop skills of keeping accounting records of small-scale business, ability to redefine risk as opportunity to make use of the expertise, ability to handle crises whenever they occur, ability to identify and use market opportunities, ability to set appropriate goals, and ability to

manage customers and maintain business ethics. Business management skills also encompass decision making, human relations, marketing, planning and goal setting (Ogwunte & Ile, 2017). Business management competencies are attributes of a person that is running a business so as to ensure its business goals are met. These skills are usually acquired through on - the - job experience or by studying them on your own time. Employers are more likely to hire employees with business management skills because such employees have knowledge on the operations of every department in a business. Business management skills also comprises planning and goal setting, human relations, decision making, management, control, negotiation, finance, marketing, managing growth, accounting and venture launch (Bumalay, Sulabo, & Ragus, 2008). Personal Entrepreneurial Skills and Employment Generation These skills include flexibility, risk taking, persistence, driver, imagination, competitiveness, innovativeness, inner control discipline, change orientation (Epelle, Orlu & Okparanta, 2017). In the same vein, Ogwunte and Ile (2017) identified personal entrepreneurial skills as the ability to identify challenges of personal entrepreneurship, ability to understand personal entrepreneurial regulations, ability to evaluate business ideas, ability to identify business resources, ability to understand the roles of commercial and development banks, knowledge of relevant markets and having self-confidence, knowledge of relevant machines, aggressiveness and resourcefulness, knowledge of relevant products, technical competencies in specific areas, negotiating and marketing skills, persuasive, leadership and financial management competencies and being answerable to myself. According to Muhyi (2017), personal entrepreneurial competencies include inner control, risk taker, innovative, change oriented, persistent, visionary leader and ability to management change. Personal entrepreneurial competencies can encompass a large range of both soft and hard skills. Because of the many business roles entrepreneurs may take on, they may also develop a variety of different skill sets to accommodate the growth of their businesses and brands. Developing the following competencies can also help one develop entrepreneurial competencies; Teamwork and leadership competencies, Communication and Listening, Customer service competencies, Financial competencies, Analytical and problem-solving competencies, Critical thinking competencies, Strategic thinking and planning competencies, Branding, marketing and networking competencies. To be a successful business owner, one may need to develop one's personal entrepreneurial competencies (Indeed Career Guide, 2020).

Technical competencies includes these competencies include team work, coaching competencies, listening competencies, technology competencies, oral communication competencies, writing competencies, interpersonal competencies, environmental monitoring competencies and organizing competencies (Epelle, Orlu & Okparanta, 2017). Technical competencies can refer to the ability to perform tasks that require the use of certain tools, whether tangible or intangible, and the technology required to master their intended uses in a variety of scenarios. Obviously, the knowledge in technical competencies is seen as practical in nature because it allows an individual to complete a chosen task in a real not theoretical, manner. Given the growth of technology within worldwide and local economies, the need for diverse technical competencies and knowledge is likely to continue to grow into the foreseeable future. The acquisition of advanced technical competencies requires specific education or training, often with practical learning components and many advanced topical elements. Technical competencies requirements are listed for the majority of career fields, with the highest concentrations on engagement in areas involving scientific, technological, engineering, computational and business capabilities. Technical competencies could also refer to the technical know-how and expertise needed to carry out or accomplish complex actions, tasks and processes relating to computational and physical technology as well as a varied group of other enterprises. Those who possess technical competencies are often referred to as "technicians", with the expression referring to audio technicians, electronics technicians, market technicians, computer technicians, engineering technicians, those who possess technology skills and a variety of other designations. Technical competencies are practical in nature, typically related to various fields (Farley, 2019). Technical competencies also refer to competencies acquired by using and gaining expertise in performing physical or digital tasks. There are many different kinds of technical competencies. Customarily, people working in mathematics, computer science, mechanics and

information technology have used many technical competencies. Today, however, many more industries rely on employees with technical knowledge. For instance, retail workers often need to know how to use point-of-sale (POS) software to do their business. Some specific examples of technical skills might include: Programming languages, Common operating systems, Project management, Technical writing, Software proficiency and data analysis. Technical competencies vary widely between businesses and job type. For computer programmers, knowledge of various coding languages is considered as technical competencies. Customer service representatives may need technical competencies relating to customer management and telephone systems. Teachers might need technical competencies related to instructional technologies and software applications ranging from student behavior monitoring to grading. Because of the availability of software programs for financial analysis, marketing, planning and other business processes, it can be enormously beneficial to develop one's technical skills. Entrepreneurs with efficient technical competencies can use software and other digital approaches for managing projects, tracking sales and revenue and measuring the performance of business growth. These competencies also aid in self-employment generation (Indeed Career Guide, 2020). Competencies on the other hand can simply be put as the ability to do things well. Computer appreciation skills can be used effectively as a cognitive tool as well as an instructional media. They can be helpful in classroom by encouraging inquiry, helping communication, constructing teaching products, and assisting students' self-expression. It is impossible not to pay attention to the significant impact of technology when discussing instruction, education, or training issues. The use of computers in education opens a new area of knowledge and offers a tool that has the potential to change some of the existing educational methods. The teacher is the key to the effective exploitation of this resource in the educational system. As computer use continues to increase in society, teachers must also prepare for the use of computers within the classroom (Gilakjanim, 2013). Ibelegbu (2013) asserted that a computer literate graduates should have the following skills: the ability to programme and control a computer for personal, academic and professional goals; the ability to use a variety of computer applications software within a personal, academic and professional context; the ability to understand the increasing social, economic and psychological impacts that computers are having on groups and individuals; the ability to make use of ideas from computer programme and computer applications as part of an individual's strategy retrieving information, communication and problem solving. The adoption and integration of information and communication technology (ICT) into the education programme of a country cannot be overemphasized. It has been discovered that knowledge of (ICT) usage improves human capacity in every field of human endeavour, including business transaction, industrial operations, educational programmes and activities and life in general (Achibong, Ogbegi, & Obildem, 2010). Hence, without ICT or Computer appreciation competencies in this era of technology, employment generation cannot be achieved. Employment Generation Employment generation is the process involved in engaging the labour force in productive activities in the economy.

Statement of the Problem

Business Education programme plays important in equipping the graduates of the programme the required competencies needed for them to be self-employed. University Business Education graduates by their education and training ought to have the required competencies that will enable them establish their own businesses and have gainful employment, maintain, sustain and secure it. Graduates of Business Education who lack the requisite competencies for employment will not be productive in the world of work or business. This brings to the front burner the question whether Business Education graduates have the required business management competencies, personal entrepreneurial competencies and technical competencies relevant for self-employment generation in south-south, Nigeria. Ogwunte and Ile (2017) observed that many Business Education graduates lack the requisite competencies for self-employment. It is on this ground that this study seeks to ascertain the core competencies required by University Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which business management competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required by Business Education graduates Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent to which personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.
3. Determine the extent to which Technical competencies are required by Business Education graduates Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were guided the study:

1. To what extent are business management competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education Graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria?
3. To what extent are technical competencies required by Business Education Graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on business management competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required by Business Education Graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on technical competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

METHOD

A descriptive survey design was chosen for the study. The population of the study consisted of 60 Post graduate Business Education students in selected tertiary institutions in south-south. The entire population size was used. This is because of its manageable number. The instrument used for the study was structured questionnaire titled: "Competencies required by Business Education graduates for self-employment in south-south" Questionnaire (CRBEGESSQ) The data collected were analyzed using mean rating and standard deviation for the research questions. The mean ratings were interpreted using the boundary limits. The analysis was done on an item by item and cluster basis, which made it practically necessary to determine the grand mean. The hypotheses were tested using T-test. The hypotheses were to be accepted when the t-cal was less than the table value and rejected when the t-critical was greater than the t-critical (table value).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent are business management competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) are required by university Business Education graduates for employment in south-south?*

Table 1: Data On the Extent Business Management Competencies as Part of Office and Information Management (OIM) Are Required by Business Education Graduates for Self-Employment In South-South.

S/N	ITEMS	Male students (16)			Female students (40)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
1.	I am competent in planning.	3.06	0.61	ME	2.88	0.58	ME	2.97	0.59	ME
2.	I am competent in making business decisions.	3.25	0.65	ME	3.05	0.61	ME	3.15	0.63	ME
3.	I am competent in Negotiating businesses	3.44	0.69	ME	2.93	0.59	ME	3.19	0.64	ME
4.	I am competent in controlling Businesses.	3.13	0.63	ME	3.0	0.60	ME	3.07	0.61	ME
5.	I am competent in relating with customers.	3.00	0.60	ME	3.00	0.60	ME	3.00	0.60	ME
	Total Mean/SD	15.88	3.18		14.86	2.98		15.38	3.07	
	Grand Mean/SD	3.18	0.64		2.97	0.59		3.08	0.61	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The data in table 1 shows that all the mean responses are at a moderate extent. This implies that the competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required of Business Education graduates for self-employment are; planning, decision-making, negotiation, business control and ability to relate with customers.

Research Question 2: *To what extent are personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education graduates for self-employment in south-south, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Data on the extent are personal entrepreneurial competencies are required by Business Education graduates for self-employment in south-south, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Male Students (16)			Female Students (40)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
6.	I am very innovative as a individual.	2.81	0.56	ME	2.80	0.56	ME	2.80	0.56	ME
7.	I am very persistent in achieving my objectives.	3.00	0.60	ME	2.88	0.58	ME	2.94	0.59	ME
8.	I have a strong orientation for success.	2.88	0.68	ME	2.60	0.52	ME	2.74	0.55	ME
9.	I am competent in motivating others to achieve set goals.	2.88	0.58	ME	2.85	0.57	ME	2.87	0.57	ME
10.	Am not rigid in achieving in accepting organizational growth.	2.88	0.58	ME	2.88	0.58	ME	2.88	0.58	ME
	Total Mean/SD	14.45	2.90		14.01	2.81		14.23	2.85	
	Grand Mean/SD	2.89	0.58		2.80	0.56		2.85	0.57	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The data in table 2 shows that all the mean responses are at a moderate extent. This implies that the personal entrepreneurial competencies required of Business Education graduates for self-employment are innovation, persistence, strong orientation for success, ability to motivate others to achieve set goals and acceptance of organizational growth.

Research Question 3: *To what extent are technical competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Data On the Extent Are Technical Competencies Required by Business Education Graduates for Effective Self-Employment in South-South, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Male Students (16)			Female Students (40)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
11.	Am competent in technical business analysis.	2.50	0.50	ME	2.25	0.45	LE	2.38	0.48	LE
12.	I have project management competence.	2.81	0.56	ME	2.15	0.43	LE	2.48	0.49	LE
13.	I am competent in data analysis. .	2.88	0.58	ME	2.40	0.48	LE	2.64	0.53	ME
14.	Am competent in environmental monitoring and analysis.	2.69	0.54	ME	2.33	0.47	LE	2.51	0.50	ME
15.	Am competent in the use of technology.	2.69	0.54	ME	2.55	0.51	ME	2.62	0.52	ME
	Total Mean/SD	13.57	2.72		11.68	2.34		12.63	2.52	
	Grand Mean/SD	2.71	0.54		2.34	0.47		2.53	0.50	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The data in table 3 shows that all the mean responses are at a moderate extent. This implies that the technical competencies required of Business Education graduates for self-employment are; technical business analysis, project management competence, data analysis, business environmental monitoring and analysis and competence in the use of technology.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on business management competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required by Business Education Graduates for self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Table 4: T-Test of Difference In The Mean Ratings Of Male And Female Respondents On Business Management Competencies As Part Of Office And Information Management (OIM) Required By Business Education Graduates Business Education Graduates For Self-Employment In South-South, Nigeria.

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign	Decision
Male Students	16	3.18	0.64	54	1.11	2.004	0.05	Accepted
Female Students	40	2.97	0.59					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 4 shows that t-calculated (1.11) is less than the t-critical (2.004). Hence, the hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and

female respondents on business management competencies required by Business Education Graduates Business Education graduates for self-employment in south-south, Nigeria..

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on personal entrepreneurial competencies as part of office and information management (OIM) required by Business Education Graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Table 5: T-test of Difference between male and female respondents on personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education Graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign	Decision
Male Students	16	2.89	0.58	54	0.53	2.004	0.05	Accepted
Female Students	40	2.80	0.56					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 5 shows that the t-calculated (0.53) is less than the t-critical (2.004). Hence, the hypotheses was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education Graduates Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on technical competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Table 6: T-test of Difference between mean ratings of male and female respondents on technical competencies required by Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign	Decision
Male Students	16	2.71	0.54	54	2.3	2.004	0.05	Rejected
Female Students	40	2.34	0.47					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 6 shows that the t-calculated (2.3) is higher than the t-critical (2.004). Hence, the hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on technical competencies required by Business Education Graduates Business Education graduates for effective self-employment in south-south, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings was done based on the purposes of the study.

From the results presented in the study as shown in research question one, it was revealed that business management competencies such as planning skills, decision making skills, negotiation skills, the ability to control business and human relation competencies are required by Business Education graduates for self-employment to a moderate extent. This finding is in agreement with the study of Okoro (2013) who noted that Business Education programme equip graduates with business management skills that will enable them create new enterprise. The finding of this study is also supported by Epelle, Orlu and Okparanta (2017) who identified business management skills as; planning and goal setting, decision making, human relations, marketing, accounting, finance management, control, negotiation, venture, launching, growth management needed for employment generation. Ogwunte and Ile (2017) also noted in their study that

Business Management competencies include the ability to supervise business effectively, ability to source funds for running of small-scale business knowledge of business registration, ability to plan for small-scale or medium-scale business, ability to develop skills of keeping accounting to redefine risk as opportunity to make use of the expertise, ability to handle crises whenever they occur, ability to identify and use market opportunities, ability to set appropriate goals, and ability to manage customers and maintain business ethics and such skills are paramount for employment in any sector of economy.

From the results in research question two shows that personal entrepreneurial competencies such innovative, change orientation, the ability to be persistent, flexibility skills and the ability to motivate others to work are moderately required by Business Education graduates for self-employment. This is evident in the respondents' responses as they agreed that personal entrepreneurial competencies required by Business Education graduates for self-employment to a moderate extent. This finding agreed with Ogwunte and Ile (2017) who opined that personal entrepreneurial competencies such as the ability to identify challenges of personal entrepreneurship, ability to understand personal entrepreneurial regulations, ability to evaluate business ideas, ability to identify business resources ability to understand the roles of commercial and development banks, knowledge of relevant markets and having self-confidence, knowledge of relevant machines, aggressiveness and resourcefulness, knowledge of relevant products, technical skills in specific areas, negotiating and marketing skills, persuasive, leadership and financial management skills and being answerable to oneself. This is in agreement with Muhyi (2017) who noted that persons entrepreneurial skills such as inner control, risk taker, innovative, change oriented, persistent, visionary leader and ability to management change are essential for employment generation.

From the findings presented in research question three, it was revealed that technical competencies were required by Business Education graduates for self-employment to a moderate extent. This implies that technical competencies such as technical writing, project management; data analysis, environmental monitoring, technology are required moderately by Business Education graduates. This was shown in the respondents' responses as they agreed that technical competencies required by Business Education graduates for self-employment to a moderate extent. This is in agreement with Epelle, Orlu and Okparanta (2017) who noted that technical competencies such as team work, coaching skills, listening skills, technology skills, oral communication skills, writing skills, interpersonal skills, environmental monitoring skills and organizing skills are essential for the world of work. This implies that technical skills are needed for employment generation.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that the competencies required by Business Education graduates for self-employment are; Business management skills, Personal entrepreneurial skills, Technical skills and Computer appreciation skills. It was also evident that there is significant difference between the core competencies required by university Business Education graduates for self-Employment .

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The managers of Business Education programme should lay much emphasis on the acquisition of the appropriate competency needed for self-employment of graduates of the programme.
2. There should be a constant collaboration with the industries so as to know the appropriate skill needed for Business Education graduates to be self-employable
3. The Curriculum of Business Education programme should be in tandem with today's competencies that are required.

REFERENCES

Achibong, I. A., Ogbegi, J. E. & Obildem, F. A. (2010). ICT Competence among Academic Staff in Universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.ccsenet.org/ciscomputerandinformationsscinee>, 8th November, 2019.

- Ajoma, C. U. (2010). Strategies for re-branding business education for better performance and higher productivity in Nigeria. A Paper Presented at the 8th Annual National Conference of the Nigerian Association of Vocational and Technical Educators (NAVTEd) at College of Education, Oju, Benue State, 7th - 10th July, 2010.
- Aliyu, M. M. (2013). Subject method for business teachers. Kaduna: Sunyo A. J. Global Limited.
- Allen, K. I. B., Ndukwe, C. I. & Orike, A. N. (2017). Entrepreneurial skills and business education students' self-reliance in Rivers State. *Rivers Business Education Journal*, 2(1), 24–25.
- Allison, M. M. (2016). Computer skills essential to break poverty cycle. Retrieved from <http://pdfserve.golegroup.com/pdfserve/getitem/>, 30th May 2019.
- Amaewhule, W. A. (2007). The world of work and the challenge of change. An Inaugural Lecture. Rivers State University.
- Amaewhule, W. A. (2014). A Guide to Entrepreneurship Development through Reflections on the World of Work, Port Harcourt: Odesaa Educational Books.
- Bhat, A. (2020). Correlational Research: Definition with Examples. Retrieved from <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/correlational-research/>, 4th February, 2020.
- Binuomote, M. O. & Okoli, B. E. (2015). Business education students' perception of the skill needs for successful entrepreneurship in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 3(7), 27-34.
- Bumalay, E. L., Sulabo, E. C. & Ragus, O. (2008). An analysis of the personal entrepreneurial competencies of students: implications to curriculum designing of entrepreneurship programme. *Research and Development Journal*, 16(2), 127-134.
- Cross, G. B. (2008). Business education microsoft. Encarata: Redmond Microsoft Corporation Pub.
- Ekong, J. E. (2017). Plugged-in, yet unplugged: problematizing the digital communications chasm of the day in the African world. Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Applications of Information and Communication Technologies to Teaching, Research and Administration. 33-41.
- Enobong, U. & Uduak, E. (2015). Employment generation for a small economy: the Nigerian case. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Studies (IJIMS)*, 2(10), 93-103.
- Epelle, B. Orlu, G. C. & Okparanta, R. (2017). Effect of entrepreneurship education on business education students for national development. *Rivers Business Education Journal*, 2(1), 129-137.
- Esene, R. A. (2017). Challenge facing office educators in the implementation of office technology and management curriculum and new technologies in polytechniques in south-south geo-political zone of Nigeria. *World Educator Forum* 1-20.
- Ezenwafor, J. I. & Olaniyi, O. N. (2017). Ratings skills needed by business education graduates for entrepreneurial development in Southwest Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research*, 4(1), 165-177.
- Ezeugbor, C. O. (2008). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence level of Nigerian tertiary institutions teachers as a challenge to harnessing the ICT gains in education edited by B. G. Nworgu, Education in the information age; Global Challenges and Enhancement Strategies, Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Ezimoyih, C.M., & Okafor, N.A. (2010). Evaluation of information and communication technology skills needed by accounting education lecturers in Nigeria. *Business Education Journal*, 10(4). Farley, A. (October 1, 2019). Technical Skills. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/items/t/technical.skills.asp>, 10th October 2019.
- Gilakjani, A. P. (2013). Factors Contributing to Teachers' Use of Computer Technology in the Classroom. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 1(3), 262-267.
- Ibelegbu, N. A. (2013). Information and communication skills needed by Business Studies teachers in junior secondary schools in Adamawa State, A Project Report Presented to the Department of Vocational Teacher Education, university of Nigeria, Nsukka in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of master of education degree (M.Ed) in Business Education.

- Igbongidi, P. (2017). Promoting gender equality through business education programme for entrepreneurship in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Advances in Sciences and Humanities Journal*, 3(2),11-13.
- Igirshar, V. U. & Ayidiowu, S. I. (2015). The impact of Business Education on growth of SMEs: A basic tool for national development. A Paper being presented at 6th National Conference and Workshop, theme: Basic Education as a Fundamental Tool to National Development, 1-14.
- Ihua-Jonathan, N. & Sobere, M. (2017). Entrepreneurship education and employability of Business Education graduands in Rivers State. *Rivers Business Education Journal*, 2(1), 216-227.
- Imeokparia, P. O. & Ediagbonya, K. (2012).Employability of business education graduates. *International Research Journal*, 3(8), 645-651. Indeed Career Guide. (January 3rd, 2020). Business management skills, definitions and examples.<https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/business-management-skills>.
- International Labour Organization (2020). Employment Generation. Retrieved fromhttps://www.ilo.org/jobspact/policy/WCMS_DOC_GJP_ARE_EMP_EN/lang--en/index.htm. 21st September, 2020.
- Lawal, A. (2014). Capital structure and the value of the firm: evidence from the Nigeria banking industry. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, 1(1), 31-41.
- Lillian, T.E. (2003). Predictors of success in the era of the boundaryless career. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/job.214>.
- Meleod, S. (2018). Maslow’s hierarchy of needs theory. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/maslow.html>, 20th October, 2020.
- Meleod, S. (2023). Maslow’s hierarchy of needs. <https://simplypsychology.org/maslow.html>.
- Muhyi, H. A. (2017). Personal entrepreneurial skills in small-scale industries in Baros District, Sukabunmi City. *Review of Integrative Business and Economic Research*, 6(3), 295-300.
- National Open University of Nigeria. (2008). Business education methods, Lagos: National Open University of Nigeria.
- Nnadozie, F. M. (2012). The irrevocable laws of business success. Port Harcourt: Majesty Press.
- Odunaike, K. Oluwafemi, I. K. O. & Epetimehin, F. M. (2012).Assessment of the quality of business education programme in selected higher institutions in Ogun State. *American Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 3(4), 140–144.
- Ogwunte, P. C. & Ile, C. (2017). Management and entrepreneurial competencies expected of Business Education Graduate workers to handle entrepreneurship challenges in Rivers State. *Rivers Business Education Journal*, 2(1), 99–107.
- Okoro, J. (2009). Why students choose business teacher education programme in Nigeria universities. *Business Education Journal*, 8(1), 7–80.
- Okoro, J. (2013). Strategies for enhancing the functionality of business studies in the universal basic education programme in South-South Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(17), 131-136.
- Olawolu, O. E. & Kaegon, L. E. S. (2012). Entrepreneurship education as tool for youth empowerment through higher education for global workplace in Rivers. A paper presented at the seventh regional conference on higher education for a globalized world organized by the 36 Higher Education Research and Policy Networks (HERPNET); holding at the University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria between 17th to 21st Sept. 2012.
- Oluwakemi, O. O., Olawale, L. A. & Qudus, O. A. (2018). Entrepreneurial skills’ acquisition and employment generation among Polytechnic graduates in South West, Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Humanities*,3(2), 1-12. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary. (2010). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Oyadongha, J. D. (2014). Promoting a mentor-mentee relationship for productivity in business in Nigeria. *Rivers Business Education Journal*,1(2), 74–83. Retrieved from <https://mp.ra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/55538/>. 21st September, 2020.
- Sulayman, D.G. & Philo, A. (2014). Role of business education in promoting entrepreneurship in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 3(4), 73- 78.
- Ubulom, W. J. & Dambo, B. I. (2016). An evaluation of the objectives of the undergraduate business education degree programmes in some Nigerian universities. Evaluation and program planning. *International Journal of Innovative Social Science Education Research*,4(1), 26-35.
- Vliet, V.V. (2018). 14 principles of management. Retrieved from <https://www.toolshero.com/management/14-principles-of-management/> 9th August, 2019
- Wagbara, S. O. (2014). Professional ethics of Business Education programme. *Rivers Business Education Journal*, 1(2), 191-199.
- Yusuf, S. A. (2014). The informal sector and employment generation in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://mp.ra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/55538/>. 21st September, 2020.